

The objective of RESiLEX is to improve the resilience and sustainability of the entire Silicon value chain and reduce EU dependence on critical raw materials for solar panel and battery production. Silicon is considered a critical raw material for the EU due to its high supply risk and economic importance, mainly because of heavy reliance on imports

Bio-sourced materials for producing new PV modules

Three types of PV modules developed by CSEM with flax backsheet

The recycling of silicon is one crucial aspect of the Resilex project, however, project partners are also exploring new ways to reduce the carbon footprint of PV panels' production. This can be achieved by substituting parts of the photovoltaic module with bio-based or low environmental impact materials, specifically, these parts are:

- The front sheet.
- The encapsulant, a transparent layer that protects and bonds the cells together.
- The backsheet, which protects the rear of the module, or the rear glass.
- The frame, which provides structural support.

Bio-based Materials and Environmental Impact

Bio-based materials are derived, in whole or in part, from biomass. They can be unprocessed natural materials (like wood or natural fibers), polymers chemically identical to fossil-based ones but derived from biomass ("drop-in"), or new polymers without fossil equivalents. There are also bio-composites, which use bio-based fibers or polymers.

The use of these materials promises a potentially lower environmental footprint compared to petroleum-derived materials, reducing dependence on fossil resources.

However, it is crucial to carefully assess their impact over the entire lifecycle of the module (from production to energy generation), as the benefits at the material level are not always guaranteed and there might be trade-offs, for example, in land or water use for the crops they are derived from. For this reason, the project proposes a selection strategy that includes environmental impact analysis via LCA (Life Cycle Assessment) and reliability tests according to photovoltaic standards.

Material Testing and Evaluation

Several tests were performed on the selected materials and the modules incorporating them, these are the ones that were included:

Peeling tests – measure the adhesion between different layers of the module.

Transmittance measurement – checks how much light passes through the front and encapsulant materials.

Barrier properties – measure how much oxygen (O₂TR) and water vapor (WVTR) can pass through the materials, critical parameters for module lifespan.

Accelerated aging tests – modules or material samples are exposed to extreme conditions to simulate their durability over time, such as:

- Damp Heat (DH): High temperature (85 °C) and high humidity (85 % RH).
- Thermal Cycling (TC): extreme temperature variations (-40 °C to 85 °C).
- Humidity-Freeze (HF): cycles of high humidity and sub-zero temperatures.extreme temperature variations (-40 °C to 85 °C) at 85% RH.

Main Results for Components

Backsheet: a bio-composite made of natural flax fibers and polypropylene (PP) resin was studied. This material passed the accelerated aging tests under Damp Heat conditions for 1000 hours without delamination. However, the adhesion with the tested encapsulants (commercial EVA and internal project encapsulant) was below the target value and further reduced after the DH test, with delamination occurring between the PP resin and the flax fibers. Thin wood was also tested as a backsheet for lightweight modules. A module with a wooden backsheet passed an aging test (Humidity-Freeze) with very low performance loss.

Although the flax backsheet has a higher environmental impact compared to conventional backsheets, its rigidity enables the removal of glass—one of the most CO₂-intensive components.

This substitution results in a lower overall environmental impact during the module's production. However, it is essential that this new module structure does not reduce the module's lifespan, as a shorter lifetime could increase the carbon footprint of the solar electricity.

Encapsulant and Front Sheet: a silane-grafted resin-based encapsulant was developed, with the potential to be bio-based in the future. This encapsulant showed barrier properties similar to a conventional material (POE).

A non-fluorinated flexible polymeric front sheet was also developed (currently not bio-based, but a step towards sustainability by avoiding fluorine). This front sheet showed superior water vapor barrier properties compared to a commercial fluorinated front sheet.

Detail of a module developed by CSEM with flax backsheet

Aging tests on small modules (mono-modules) using the encapsulants developed by the project (CSEM TPO and TPOUV) with advanced solar cells (SHJ) yielded very encouraging results. Most modules significantly exceeded the standard Damp Heat aging requirements (power loss less than 5% after 1000 hours), lasting 1.5 or even 3 times the standard duration. Different degradation patterns were observed, including blackening in glass/glass configurations (potentially linked to ion migration from the glass) and delamination under busbars in modules with a commercial encapsulant. Lamination trials were conducted to produce fully polymeric modules (front sheet, encapsulant, and back sheet with SHJ cells).

Lamination trials with polymer stack with no cell break with RESILEX project encapsulant

Lamination trials with polymer stack with no cell break and commercial encapsulant.

Frame: the frame is an important component for the mechanical stability of modules, especially larger and thinner ones. The conventional aluminium frame has a high environmental impact. The use of wood as an alternative to aluminium for frames was studied. Different wood species were evaluated, and acacia was found to be the most promising due to its mechanical properties after aging tests.

Computer simulations suggest that a wooden frame could provide similar mechanical stability to aluminium, although it would require a larger cross-section and be heavier. Simulations indicate that the greatest risk of breakage in framed modules (both aluminium and wood) occurs in the glass during positive pressure tests. A challenge with wood is its non-homogeneity (e.g., the presence of knots), which can affect its strength. The next step will be to test wooden frames on standard-sized modules to confirm the simulation results.

Wrap up

Accelerated aging tests on mini and mono-modules incorporating these new materials, particularly the encapsulants developed by the project, have shown good initial reliability, significantly exceeding standard Damp Heat aging requirements.

The use of wooden frames appears to be a promising alternative to aluminium for reducing the carbon footprint, with simulations and sample tests supporting its feasibility, although challenges remain (weight, material homogeneity). Further studies and tests are needed (including final LCA and safety tests) to fully validate the suitability and environmental benefits of these materials on standard-sized modules.